

Statement and proof of a new general Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality theorem

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Abstract: In this study, we establish a theorem that provides a new type of Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality. It has the characteristic of being very general and flexible, using a special primitive-type operator, four intermediate functions and seven adaptable parameters. The corresponding proof has the originality of combining a new integral result and "old" Hardy integral inequalities, which merge thanks to appropriate choices of the parameters. Several examples are provided to demonstrate how the theorem can be applied in certain tractable settings.

Key words: Hardy integral inequality, Hilbert integral inequality, Hölder integral inequality.

1. Introduction

Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequalities have always been of great interest in mathematical analysis. The formal statements of two key inequalities of this type are given below.

- Hardy integral inequality: Let $p > 1$ and $f : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be a function. Then we have

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-p} \left[\int_0^x f(t) dt \right]^p dx \leq \left(\frac{p}{p-1} \right)^p \int_0^{+\infty} f^p(x) dx, \quad (1)$$

provided that the integrals converge.

- Hilbert integral inequality: Let $f, g : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be two functions. Then we have

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{f(x)g(y)}{x+y} dx dy \leq \pi \left[\int_0^{+\infty} f^2(x) dx \right]^{1/2} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} g^2(y) dy \right]^{1/2},$$

provided that the integrals converge.

See [10] for the technical details, including the corresponding proofs.

Since their publication, these inequalities have been studied extensively and have inspired many advances. In particular, in the last two decades, research on Hardy-Hilbert-type inequalities has intensified. Many papers have been published exploring various generalizations and practical applications. The following strong references support this claim: [1–8, 11–31]. Taken together, they highlight the continuing relevance and adaptability of the Hardy and Hilbert integral inequalities in modern mathematical research.

In this study, we propose to go further in this direction, with the intention of making a Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality as general as possible, i.e., with multiple functions and parameters. We proceed in two

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steps. First, we give a general statement about an inequality centered on a double integral of the following form:

$$” \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy, ”$$

where F , G , H and K denote customisable functions. The originality of this result lies in the wide range of functions and parameters involved. In particular, we highlight the fact that the parameters can take negative values, which opens up the use of bivariate functions based on the ratio y/x . Bivariate functions of the classical product xy can also be considered. As a final step, we combine this new result with some "old" Hardy integral inequalities established in [10], which extend the one in Equation (1). This leads to the statement of a new theorem, which gives an integral inequality for a double integral of the following form:

$$” \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^\mu[f](x)D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^\nu[g](y)H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy, ”$$

where $D_r[h]$ refers to a particular primitive-type operator, equal to $\int_0^x h(t)dt$ or $\int_x^{+\infty} h(t)dt$, depending on some threshold for r . As sketched by the expression of the above double integral, numerous functions and parameters are involved and can be configured according to the desired mathematical context. The technical details of these aspects are given in this study. Several examples involving ratio and exponential functions will also be developed to see how our results can be applied and how they innovate in the field of Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequalities.

The rest of the study is planned according to the following sections: Section 2 presents the statements of the main propositions, and highlights the theorem in question. It also contains examples. Section 3 contains the proofs of our new results. A conclusion is given in Section 4.

2. Results

First, we give the statement of two propositions needed to prove the main theorem, called secondary results.

2.1. Secondary results

The following statement is well-known, and can be found in [10].

Proposition 2.1. [10, Theorem 330] *Let $p > 1$ and $f : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be a function.*

1. *Let $r > 1$. Then we have*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-r} \left[\int_0^x f(t)dt \right]^p dx \leq \left(\frac{p}{r-1} \right)^p \int_0^{+\infty} x^{p-r} f^p(x)dx,$$

provided that the integrals converge.

2. *Let $r < 1$. Then we have*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-r} \left[\int_x^{+\infty} f(t)dt \right]^p dx \leq \left(\frac{p}{1-r} \right)^p \int_0^{+\infty} x^{p-r} f^p(x)dx,$$

provided that the integrals converge.

The presented integral inequalities are thus valid under different primitive-type integrals, i.e., $\int_0^x h(t)dt$ or $\int_x^{+\infty} h(t)dt$, depending on the threshold 1 for r . This has led us to the definition of a primitive-type operator, described below. For any $r \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{1\}$ and $h : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$, we set

$$D_r[h](x) = \begin{cases} \int_0^x h(t)dt & \text{if } r > 1 \\ \int_x^{+\infty} h(t)dt & \text{if } r < 1. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

With the use of this operator, the inequalities in Proposition 2.1 can be re-formulated as follows:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-r} D_r^p[f](x)dx \leq \left(\frac{p}{|r-1|}\right)^p \int_0^{+\infty} x^{p-r} f^p(x)dx, \quad (3)$$

provided that the integrals converge. We thus have a unified integral inequality, which will be a part of the proof of our main theorem.

Independently of the above, we introduce a proposition which gives a new general integral inequality. This inequality is of the Hilbert type.

Proposition 2.2. *Let $p, q > 1$ such that $1/p + 1/q = 1$, $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$, $\gamma, \tau \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, and $F, G, H, K : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be four functions. Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H(x^\gamma y)K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p + 1)} F^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q + 1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p} = \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} H^p(z) dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1} K^q(z) dz \right]^{1/q}, \quad (4)$$

provided that the integrals converge.

The interest of this proposition is its generality and the closed form expression of the upper bound. In particular, the parameters α , β , γ and τ can be positive or negative, provided that the integrals involved converge. We are thus able to consider bivariate functions depending on y/x , y/\sqrt{x} , and xy , among others. This, combined with the customisable functions F , G , H and K , allows the result to be adapted to various mathematical scenarios involving integral inequalities.

Some examples of applications are given below.

General examples: Selecting the values $\gamma, \tau \in \{-1, 1\}$, we can deal with a double integral of the following forms:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H\left(\frac{y}{x}\right)K\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) dx dy,$$

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) K(xy) dx dy, \quad (5)$$

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H(xy) K\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) dx dy$$

and

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H(xy) K(xy) dx dy.$$

These forms correspond to those considered in certain Hilbert-type integral inequalities. Some examples can be found in the book [27].

First special example: As a more specific example involving ratio functions, taking into account the form in Equation (5) obtained with $\gamma = -1$ and $\tau = 1$, and considering

$$H(t) = \frac{t^\lambda}{(1+t)^{2\lambda}}, \quad K(t) = \frac{1}{(1+t)^\sigma},$$

with $t > 0$, $\lambda, \sigma \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, we get the following general double integral:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha+\lambda} y^{\beta+\lambda} F(x)G(y) \frac{1}{(x+y)^{2\lambda}} \frac{1}{(1+xy)^\sigma} dx dy.$$

Proposition 2.2 gives an upper bound for it. More precisely, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha+\lambda} y^{\beta+\lambda} F(x)G(y) \frac{1}{(x+y)^{2\lambda}} \frac{1}{(1+xy)^\sigma} dx dy \\ & \leq \Psi \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\beta p+1} F^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)} G^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where, based on Equation (4),

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi &= \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} \frac{z^{\lambda p}}{(1+z)^{2\lambda p}} dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\alpha q} \frac{1}{(1+z)^{\sigma q}} dz \right]^{1/q} \\ &= \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{z^{(\beta+\lambda)p}}{(1+z)^{2\lambda p}} dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{z^{\alpha q}}{(1+z)^{\sigma q}} dz \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

provided that the integrals converge.

Using a known integral result (see [9, 3.1943, with $\beta = 1$]) and introducing the standard gamma function $\Gamma(a) = \int_0^{+\infty} t^{a-1} e^{-t} dt$ with $a > 0$, we have

$$\Psi = \left[\frac{\Gamma[(\beta+\lambda)p+1] \Gamma[(\lambda-\beta)p-1]}{\Gamma(2\lambda p)} \right]^{1/p} \left[\frac{\Gamma(\alpha q+1) \Gamma[(\sigma-\alpha)q-1]}{\Gamma(\sigma q)} \right]^{1/q},$$

provided that $\lambda, \sigma, (\beta+\lambda)p+1, (\lambda-\beta)p-1, \alpha q+1, (\sigma-\alpha)q-1 > 0$. Taking into account this explicit constant, we thus have, to the best of our knowledge, a new Hilbert-type integral inequality.

Second special example: Let us now show how ratio and exponential functions can be involved in our result.

Considering

$$H(t) = e^{-\lambda t}, \quad K(t) = \frac{1}{(1+t)^\sigma},$$

with $t > 0$, $\lambda, \sigma \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ in the main double integral of Proposition 2.2, we get

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x) G(y) e^{-\lambda x^\gamma y} \frac{1}{(1+x^\tau y)^\sigma} dx dy.$$

Proposition 2.2 gives the following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x) G(y) e^{-\lambda x^\gamma y} \frac{1}{(1+x^\tau y)^\sigma} dx dy \\ & \leq \Sigma \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} F^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} e^{-p\lambda z} dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1} \frac{1}{(1+z)^{\sigma q}} dz \right]^{1/q},$$

provided that the integrals converge. After some standard integral manipulations, we obtain

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \frac{1}{(p\lambda)^{(\beta p+1)/p}} [\Gamma(\beta p+1)]^{1/p} \left[\frac{\Gamma[(\alpha q+1)/\tau] \Gamma[\sigma q - (\alpha q+1)/\tau]}{\Gamma(\sigma q)} \right]^{1/q},$$

provided that $\lambda, \sigma, \beta p+1, (\alpha q+1)/\tau, \sigma q - (\alpha q+1)/\tau > 0$. Thus, to the best of our knowledge, we have a new Hilbert-type integral inequality with this multiparameter constant.

We end this subsection with two technical remarks discussing some aspects or extensions of Proposition 2.2.

Remark 2.1. *It is important to note that we can use Proposition 2.2 for a double integral of the following form:*

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x) G(y) L(x^\gamma y) dx dy,$$

where $L : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ is a function. By direct analogy, this corresponds to the case $H = L$ and $K = 1$, which is excluded a priori due to the non-convergence of the integrals in the upper bounds. A special manipulation has to be done, which is described below. Introducing a parameter $\theta \in (0, 1)$, we can write $L(x^\gamma y) = L^\theta(x^\gamma y) L^{1-\theta}(x^\gamma y)$, so that we deal with

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x) G(y) L^\theta(x^\gamma y) L^{1-\theta}(x^\gamma y) dx dy,$$

which corresponds to the form of the double integral in Proposition 2.2 with $H = L^\theta$, $K = L^{1-\theta}$ and $\tau = \gamma$. Proposition 2.2 thus gives a suitable upper bound in this case, with a new parameter θ .

Remark 2.2. In the same framework, just replacing $H(x^\gamma y)$ by $H(xy^\gamma)$, a variant of the result in Proposition 2.2 is

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x)G(y)H(xy^\gamma)K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \chi_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma,\tau,p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-(\beta p+1)/\gamma} F^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\chi_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma,\tau,p} = \frac{1}{|\gamma|^{1/p}} \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\beta p+1)/\gamma-1} H^p(z) dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1} K^q(z) dz \right]^{1/q},$$

provided that the integrals converge. The proof follows the lines of that of Proposition 2.2.

2.2. Main result

Our main result is the theorem below, which has the feature of combining the results in Propositions 2.1 and 2.2 to establish a new Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality.

Theorem 2.1. Let $p, q > 1$ such that $1/p + 1/q = 1$, $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$, $\gamma, \tau \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ such that $\gamma(\beta p + 1) \neq 1$ and $(\alpha q + 1)/\tau \neq 1$, $\mu > 1/p$, $\nu > 1/q$ and $f, g, H, K : [0, +\infty) \mapsto [0, +\infty)$ be four functions. We consider the operator $D_\tau[h]$ described in Equation (2). Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^\mu[f](x) D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^\nu[g](y) H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \Pi_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma,\tau,\mu,\nu,p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - \gamma(\beta p+1)} f^{\mu p}(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q+1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma,\tau,\mu,\nu,p} &= \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left(\frac{\mu p}{|\gamma(\beta p+1)-1|} \right)^\mu \left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1|} \right)^\nu \times \\ & \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} H^p(z) dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1} K^q(z) dz \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

provided that the integrals converge.

Thanks to the flexibility in the definition of $D_\tau[h]$ in Equation (2), and the presence of the four functions f , g , H and K , and the seven parameters p , α , β , γ , τ , μ and ν , this theorem provides a very general Hardy-Hilbert-type integral inequality covering many standard cases and new ones. As for Proposition 2.2, we highlight the fact that α , β , γ and τ can be positive or negative, which provides considerable flexibility in applying the theorem.

Drawing inspiration from the examples in the previous subsection, we present some applications of this theorem below.

First special example: Considering $\gamma = -1$, $\tau = 1$, the ratio functions

$$H(t) = \frac{t^\lambda}{(1+t)^{2\lambda}}, \quad K(t) = \frac{1}{(1+t)^\sigma},$$

with $t > 0$, $\lambda, \sigma \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, and $\mu = \nu = 1$ to simplify the situation, Theorem 2.1 gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha+\lambda} y^{\beta+\lambda} D_{-(\beta p+1)}[f](x) D_{\alpha q+1}[g](y) \frac{1}{(x+y)^{2\lambda}} \frac{1}{(1+xy)^\sigma} dx dy \\ & \leq \Xi \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{(\beta+1)p+1} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{q(1-\alpha)-1} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where, based on Equation (6) and some integral developments,

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi &= \frac{p}{|\beta p + 2|} \frac{1}{|\alpha|} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{z^{(\beta+\lambda)p}}{(1+z)^{2\lambda p}} dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{z^{\alpha q}}{(1+z)^{\sigma q}} dz \right]^{1/q} \\ &= \frac{p}{|\beta p + 2|} \frac{1}{|\alpha|} \left[\frac{\Gamma[(\beta+\lambda)p+1] \Gamma[(\lambda-\beta)p-1]}{\Gamma(2\lambda p)} \right]^{1/p} \left[\frac{\Gamma(\alpha q+1) \Gamma[(\sigma-\alpha)q-1]}{\Gamma(\sigma q)} \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

provided that the integrals converge, which include the conditions $\lambda, \sigma, (\beta+\lambda)p+1, (\lambda-\beta)p-1, \alpha q+1, (\sigma-\alpha)q-1 > 0$.

To precise the idea, if we further assume that $-(\beta p+1) < 1$ and $\alpha q+1 > 1$, thanks to the definition of $D_r[h]$, this inequality reads as

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha+\lambda} y^{\beta+\lambda} \left[\int_0^x f(t) dt \right] \left[\int_y^{+\infty} g(t) dt \right] \frac{1}{(x+y)^{2\lambda}} \frac{1}{(1+xy)^\sigma} dx dy \\ & \leq \Xi \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{(\beta+1)p+1} f^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{q(1-\alpha)-1} g^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

To the best of our knowledge, such a mixture of primitives combined with complex power and ratio power functions is new in the literature of integral inequalities.

Second special example: For the sake of variety, we now consider ratio and exponential functions. We take

$$H(t) = e^{-\lambda t}, \quad K(t) = \frac{1}{(1+t)^\sigma},$$

with $t > 0$, $\lambda, \sigma \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ in the main double integral of Theorem 2.1. So we have the following main double integral:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^\mu[f](x) D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^\nu[g](y) e^{-\lambda x^\gamma y} \frac{1}{(1+x^\tau y)^\sigma} dx dy.$$

Theorem 2.1 gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^\mu[f](x) D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^\nu[g](y) e^{-\lambda x^\gamma y} \frac{1}{(1+x^\tau y)^\sigma} dx dy \\ & \leq \Omega \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - \gamma(\beta p+1)} f^{\mu p}(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q+1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left(\frac{\mu p}{|\gamma(\beta p + 1) - 1|} \right)^\mu \left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1|} \right)^\nu \times \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} e^{-p\lambda z} dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1} \frac{1}{(1+z)^{\sigma q}} dz \right]^{1/q},$$

provided that the integrals converge. After some standard integral manipulations, we obtain

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left(\frac{\mu p}{|\gamma(\beta p + 1) - 1|} \right)^\mu \left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1|} \right)^\nu \times \frac{1}{(p\lambda)^{(\beta p + 1)/p} [\Gamma(\beta p + 1)]^{1/p}} \left[\frac{\Gamma[(\alpha q + 1)/\tau] \Gamma[\sigma q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau]}{\Gamma(\sigma q)} \right]^{1/q},$$

provided that $\lambda, \sigma, \beta p + 1, (\alpha q + 1)/\tau, \sigma q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau > 0$.

To precise the idea, if we further assume that $\gamma(\beta p + 1) < 1$ and $(\alpha q + 1)/\tau > 1$, thanks to the definition of $D_r[h]$, the obtained inequality reads as

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta \left[\int_0^x f(t) dt \right]^\mu \left[\int_y^{+\infty} g(t) dt \right]^\nu e^{-\lambda x^\gamma y} \frac{1}{(1+x^\tau y)^\sigma} dx dy \\ & \leq \Omega \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - \gamma(\beta p + 1)} f^{\mu p}(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy \right]^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

It is a new Hardy-Hilbert-type integral in the literature to the best of our knowledge.

These are just two special examples. The theorem is much more general, and there are many other possible applications.

We end this subsection by a technical remark.

Remark 2.3. *In the light of Remark 2.2, and the proof of Theorem 2.1, just replacing $H(x^\gamma y)$ by $H(xy^\gamma)$, the following inequality holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p + 1)}^\mu [f](x) D_{(\alpha q + 1)/\tau}^\nu [g](y) H(xy^\gamma) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \Upsilon_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, \mu, \nu, p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - (\beta p + 1)/\gamma} f^{\mu p}(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, \mu, \nu, p} &= \frac{1}{|\gamma|^{1/q}} \frac{1}{|\tau|^{1/q}} \left(\frac{\mu p}{|(\beta p + 1)/\gamma - 1|} \right)^\mu \left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1|} \right)^\nu \times \\ & \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\beta p + 1)/\gamma - 1} H^p(z) dz \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1} K^q(z) dz \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

provided that the integrals converge. The proof follows the lines of that of Theorem 2.1. This result can be viewed as a variant of this theorem.

3. Proofs

This section contains the proofs of the new results, namely, Proposition 2.2 and Theorem 2.1.

Proof of Proposition 2.2. Using a suitable decomposition of the main double integral and applying the Hölder integral inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x) G(y) H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} y^\beta F(x) H(x^\gamma y) \times x^\alpha G(y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\
 &\leq R^{1/p} S^{1/q},
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where

$$R = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} y^{\beta p} F^p(x) H^p(x^\gamma y) dx dy$$

and

$$S = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha q} G^q(y) K^q(x^\tau y) dx dy.$$

Let us now examine expressions for R and S .

Expression for R . The Fubini-Tonelli integral theorem allows us to change the order of integration, and we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 R &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} y^{\beta p} F^p(x) H^p(x^\gamma y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} F^p(x) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\beta p} H^p(x^\gamma y) dy \right] dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Applying the change of variables $z = x^\gamma y$ with respect to y , so that $y = z/x^\gamma$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^{+\infty} F^p(x) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\beta p} H^p(x^\gamma y) dy \right] dx \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} F^p(x) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \left(\frac{z}{x^\gamma} \right)^{\beta p} H^p(z) \frac{1}{x^\gamma} dz \right] dx \\
 &= \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} H^p(z) dz \right] \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} F^p(x) dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

We therefore have

$$R = \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} H^p(z) dz \right] \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} F^p(x) dx. \tag{8}$$

Expression for S . We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha q} G^q(y) K^q(x^\tau y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} G^q(y) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha q} K^q(x^\tau y) dx \right] dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

Applying the change of variables $z = x^\tau y$ with respect to x , so that $x = (z/y)^{1/\tau}$, taking into account that $\tau \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} G^q(y) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\alpha q} K^q(x^\tau y) dx \right] dy \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} G^q(y) \left[\frac{1}{|\tau|} \int_0^{+\infty} \left(\frac{z}{y} \right)^{\alpha q/\tau} K^q(z) \frac{1}{y^{1/\tau}} z^{1/\tau-1} dz \right] dy \\ &= \frac{1}{|\tau|} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1} K^q(z) dz \right] \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy. \end{aligned}$$

We therefore have

$$S = \frac{1}{|\tau|} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1} K^q(z) dz \right] \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy. \quad (9)$$

Combining Equations (7), (8) and (9), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta F(x) G(y) H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \left\{ \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{\beta p} H^p(z) dz \right] \int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} F^p(x) dx \right\}^{1/p} \times \\ & \left\{ \frac{1}{|\tau|} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} z^{(\alpha q+1)/\tau-1} K^q(z) dz \right] \int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy \right\}^{1/q} \\ & = \Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} F^p(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} G^q(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p}$ is given in Equation (4).

This ends the proof of Proposition 2.2. \square

Proof of Theorem 2.1. Applying the first point of Proposition 2.2 with $F = D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^\mu[f]$ and $G = D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^\nu[g]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^\mu[f](x) D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^\nu[g](y) H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^{\mu p}[f](x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q+1)/\tau} D_{(\alpha q+1)/\tau}^{\nu q}[g](y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p}$ is given in Equation (4).

Now, applying Proposition 2.1 under the form in Equation (3) with $r = \gamma(\beta p+1)$ and μp instead of p , we get

$$\int_0^{+\infty} x^{-\gamma(\beta p+1)} D_{\gamma(\beta p+1)}^{\mu p}[f](x) dx \leq \left(\frac{\mu p}{|\gamma(\beta p+1) - 1|} \right)^{\mu p} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - \gamma(\beta p+1)} f^{\mu p}(x) dx. \quad (11)$$

Doing the same with $r = (\alpha q + 1)/\tau$, g instead of f , and νq instead of p , we find that

$$\int_0^{+\infty} y^{-(\alpha q + 1)/\tau} D_{(\alpha q + 1)/\tau}^{\nu q}[g](y) dy \leq \left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1|} \right)^{\nu q} \int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy. \quad (12)$$

It follows from Equations (10), (11) and (12) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} x^\alpha y^\beta D_{\gamma(\beta p + 1)}^\mu[f](x) D_{(\alpha q + 1)/\tau}^\nu[g](y) H(x^\gamma y) K(x^\tau y) dx dy \\ & \leq \Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p} \left[\left(\frac{\mu p}{|\gamma(\beta p + 1) - 1|} \right)^{\mu p} \int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - \gamma(\beta p + 1)} f^{\mu p}(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \times \\ & \quad \left[\left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1|} \right)^{\nu q} \int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy \right]^{1/q} \\ & = \Pi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, \mu, \nu, p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} x^{\mu p - \gamma(\beta p + 1)} f^{\mu p}(x) dx \right]^{1/p} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} y^{\nu q - (\alpha q + 1)/\tau} g^{\nu q}(y) dy \right]^{1/q}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Pi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, \mu, \nu, p} = \left(\frac{\mu p}{|\gamma(\beta p + 1) - 1|} \right)^\mu \left(\frac{\nu q}{|(\alpha q + 1)/\tau - 1|} \right)^\nu \Phi_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau, p},$$

which corresponds to the expression in Equation (6). This concludes the proof. \square

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, we have contributed to the field of Hardy-Hilbert integral inequalities by establishing a general theorem, with exact expression of the upper bound including the constant factor. This generality is characterized by a special primitive-type operator, four intermediate functions, and seven adjustable parameters. The proof is original in that it unites a new integral result with classical Hardy integral inequalities through careful parameter selection.

One limitation of this study is that we did not investigate the optimality of the obtained constant, which is difficult to establish due to the multiple functions and parameters involved. This is clearly a challenging task for future research. Additionally, considering a triple integral as the main term or integrals of larger dimensions remains mathematically interesting.

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